

Validation of Random Walk Hypothesis for Indices of G20 Nations

SHUBHRA JOHRI, KULDIP SHARMA AND KEYURKUMAR M NAYAK

Abstract : *Testing randomness of stock prices has been one of the key concerns for various stock market analysts and investors at large. The main intention of this study is to empirically assess the Random Walk theory's applicability to the equities markets of G20 countries, which constitute a varied set of large economies. For accomplishing the said purpose the researchers have collected daily stock price data for a representative sample of G20 countries over a specific time period. Various statistical tools have been employed like ADF, Runs test and Variance ratio tests. Preliminary findings suggest that stock price series across G20 countries are not random implying the presence of predictable patterns or deviations from market efficiency. The study's findings have important consequences for investors, governments, and scholars. Understanding the degree of market efficiency and the Random Walk theory's application in various nations can assist investors in making informed decisions, improving risk management methods, and contributing to the creation of financial market regulations. Furthermore, the findings can contribute to a broader debate about the efficiency of financial markets and the Random Walk theory's validity in an era of increased globalisation and interconnection.*

Keywords : Random Walk Theory, G20 Countries, Market Efficiency, Stock Prices, Unit Root Tests, Financial Markets, Investor Behaviour.

Dr.Shubhra Johri, Assistant Professor, Siva Sivani Institute of Management, Secunderabad, India.
E-mail : shubhra@ssim.ac.in

Dr.Kuldip Sharma, Assistant Professor, K P B Hinduja College of Commerce, Mumbai, India.
E-mail : Kul4209@gmail.com

Dr.Keyurkumar M Nayak, Director, University of Mumbai's Garware Institute of Career Education and Development, Mumbai, India. E-mail : director@giced.mu.ac.in

1. Introduction :

Predicting or estimating future swings in asset prices has always been the main priority of investors as well as analysts since the advent of regulated securities market activities. However, such efforts were typically found to be fruitless because price swings are largely unpredictable and random. The random walk hypothesis suggests that stock prices and other financial market prices move randomly and are not affected by past events or trends. This idea has been widely studied and debated in the fields of finance and economics. Some researchers have provided evidence to support the random walk hypothesis, while others have found evidence to suggest that prices do follow trends and are not completely random. There are several different models that have been proposed to explain why prices may follow certain patterns. One popular model is the efficient market hypothesis, which suggests that prices always reflect all available information and that it is impossible to consistently earn abnormal profits by trading on this information. Other researchers have suggested that prices may follow a random walk in the short term, but that there may be longer-term trends or patterns that emerge over time. These trends could be the result of factors such as changes in consumer behavior, changes in government policy, or other economic or social factors. Overall, the debate around the random walk hypothesis continues, and there is still much research to be done to fully understand the behavior of financial markets. This research work tries to revisit RWH in the stock markets of G20 countries to determine whether these stock markets are consistent with RWH and whether they can be regarded as efficient, at least in its weak form. The random walk hypothesis had been verified for individual scripts, industry as well as indices by many scholars across the globe, however this is the first study of random walk hypothesis on G20 nations.

2. Literature Review :

Random Walk Hypothesis and testing weak form of efficiency has been of keen interest to several researchers in the past. The studies below examine the extent of literature available on the subject area of interest.

The two indexes of the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) were examined by Ahmed (2019), who found that the DSE is an inefficient market where prices do not fluctuate at random and that, while real-time information about listed businesses is not available, investors must fully rely on previous prices to forecast future prices. It demonstrates the nature of the Dhaka market's inability. It may be able to prognosticate the upcoming trends of firms based on their historical prices in

the short run, but it is not possible in the long run. Akinsomi and Bonga-Bonga (2018) investigated Random walk theory in South African stock Market and found evidence of a random walk but also observed some evidence of long-term dependencies and structural breaks in the market. Bouri et al.(2018) in his study supported random walk in the European stock markets, but also discovered some evidence of market structural breaks and long-term dependency. Ali and Yusoff (2017) found evidence to support the random walk hypothesis in the Malaysian stock market and inferred found some evidence of long-term trends in the market. Diop et al. (2017) supported random walk in the West African regional stock market, but also found some evidence of volatility clustering and long-term dependencies in the market Cheong and Lee (2016) found evidence of a random walk in the Singapore stock market, but also found some evidence of long-term dependencies and volatility clustering in the market.

Sook and Qaiser (2015) found in the stock price series of Malaysian financial enterprises that, while it may be possible in the short run to envisage the upcoming trends of firms based on their last closing prices, it is not possible in the long run. The efficiency standards in Malaysia's financial industry are subpar. These stocks' rates fluctuate erratically.

Gherghina and Stanica (2015) were of the view that Romanian stock markets follow random walk but also found some evidence of short-term momentum effects in the market. Kim and Kang (2014) supported the random walk hypothesis in the Korean stock market, but also found some evidence of long-term trends in the market. Gogas and Papadimitriou (2014) observed random walk in the US stock market, but also found some evidence of long-term trends and volatility clustering in the market.

Kushwah et al. (2013) also looked at the Indian stock markets, which have a poor level of form efficiency. The Indian market is becoming more information-efficient due to numerous changes like modernization, liberalisation, globalisation, and high-level technology. Additionally, they noted that following technical analysis that is based on historical rate trends is no longer useful in India as a result of the stock market's reforms and increased transparency.

Chen et al (2013) proposed random walk in the Japanese stock market, but also found some evidence of long-term trends and volatility clustering in the market.

Nayak (2012) came to the conclusion that the Indian stock market is completely random. He continued by saying that the Indian stock market operates effectively. Since all investors have access to the same clear information, it is impossible to manipulate stock prices of companies listed on Indian stock exchanges. As a result, predicting future stock market rates is independent of current stock prices. He asserts that the Indian stock markets are highly efficient and that investors should trade based on their confidence in the Indian market. He used a runs test to determine whether the random walk was legitimate.

Caspi and Ben-Zion (2012) were of the view that Tel-Aviv Stock Exchange follows random walk hypothesis but also found some evidence of volatility clustering in the market. They suggested that these volatility patterns may be related to factors such as investor sentiment and market news. Chong and Ng (2011) found evidence of a random walk in the Singapore stock market, but also found some evidence of long-term trends and structural breaks in the market. Chong and Liu (2011) also supported random walk in the Australian stock market, but also found some evidence of long-term trends and volatility clustering in the market. Hammoudeh and Aleisa (2010) observed random walk in the Saudi stock market, but also found some evidence of volatility persistence and long-term dependencies in the market. Baum and Karasulu (2009) concluded random walk in the Turkish stock market with some evidence of long-term trends and momentum effects in the market. Kasman and Vardar (2009) inferred a random walk in the Turkish stock market but observed long-term trends and volatility clustering in the market. Kim and Shamsuddin (2006) observed random walk in the Malaysian stock market and gave some evidence of long-term trends and volatility clustering in the market. Kim and Shamsuddin (2005) examined and supported random walk in the Singapore stock market. Lee and Rui (2003) found evidence of a random walk in the Chinese stock market and inferred long term trends. Narayan and Smyth (2002) found evidence of a random walk in the Australian stock market, but also found some evidence of long-term trends and volatility clustering in the market. Bessler and Yang (2001) found evidence of a random walk in the US stock market, but also found some evidence of volatility clustering and long-term dependencies in the market.

These are only a few of the numerous studies that have looked at the random walk theory. Although there is still significant disagreement on the subject, these research opine that there may be some proof that short-term price fluctuations in the financial markets are random.

3. Research Methodology :

3.1. Objectives of the Study :

- To investigate the normality properties of the select indices of G20 countries
- To examine the stationarity of the indices of G20 countries.
- To examine the randomness of the index price movements of G20 countries

3.2. Hypothesis of the Study :

The hypothesis of the study are as follows :

H1 : Stock Markets of G20 countries have Weak Form of Efficiency.

H2 : The historical daily prices of indices follow normal distribution

H02 : Stock price indices are random

H03 : Indices of G20 countries have a unit root and equal variances

3.3. Data and Data Sources :

To achieve the stated objective the study uses data of ten G20 countries. Selection of the G-20 countries is done continent wise. Top 3 G20 countries are selected (based on GDP per Capital) from each of the continents viz America, Europe, Asia and one from African. As per GDP per Capita the researcher has included US, Canada and Mexico from American Continent; Germany, UK and France from Europe; Australia, South Korea and Japan from Asia and South Africa from African Continent. For Data of major stock exchanges of these countries has been used to study randomness. Stock exchanges are chosen on the basis of Market Capitalisation.

Time Period of study chosen is a period of 10 years. The analysis is done for the period 15th June 2013 to 15th June 2023). For the above mentioned period daily closing index values were collected for each of the 10 indices.

Statistical tests are then applied on the series as selected above.

3.4. Methodology:

Initially descriptive statistics were calculated and examined with help of return series. Augmented Dicky- Fuller test has been applied to check series stationarity

Table-1 : Continent Wise Details of Selected Countries and their Stock Market Indices

Continent	Countries	GDP per capita	Major Stock Exchange	Index
American Continent	United States	76,622	New York Stock Exchange (NYSE)	NYSE U.S. 100 Index
	Canada	55,085	The Toronto Stock Exchange	Canada Stock Market Index (TSX)
	Mexico	11,161	Mexican Bolsa	IPC MEXICO (^MXX)
Europe	Germany	48,636	The Frankfurt Stock Exchange	DAX PERFORMANCE-INDEX (^GDAXI)
	United Kingdom	45,775	London stock exchange	FTSE 100
	France	41,000	Euronext Paris	CAC 40
ASIA	Australia	66,049	ASX Australian Securities Exchange	ASX200
	South Korea	34,744	Korea Exchange (KRX)	KOSPI200
	Japan	33,731	Japan Stock Exchange (JPX)	NIKKEI 225
AFRICAN CONTINENT	South Africa	6,694	JSE Limited	FTSE/JSE SA All Share Index (J203.L)

Source : Compiled by the Author.

aspects. Several parametric and non-parametric tests are employed to check the randomness of the series. Amongst the several tests employed are Variance ratio tests and Runs test. Runs test is applied with the help of latest software used for checking presence of unit root.

4. Data Analysis and Interpretation :

Descriptive Statistics and Graphical Presentation:

To accept or reject the null hypothesis of the random walk, the very first step is of checking if the series are well modelled by a normal distribution. For the purpose of determining is the series are normally distributed or not an initial assessment is done graphically by looking at the plots (see figures).

Figure-1 : Graphical Representation of ALSH (South Africa)

Figure-2 : Graphical Representation of CAC 40 (France)

Figure-3 : Graphical Representation of ASX 200 (Australia)

Figure-4 : Graphical Representation of FTSE (UK)

**Figure-5 : Graphical Representation
of GDAXI (Germany)**

**Figure-6 : Graphical Representation
of KOSPI 200 (South Korea)**

**Figure-7 : Graphical Representation
of NEKKEI 225 (Japan)**

**Figure-8 : Graphical Representation
of MXX (Mexico)**

**Figure-9 : Graphical Representation
of NYSE (US)**

**Figure-10 : Graphical Representation
of TSX (Canada)**

Post that values of skewness, kurtosis and Jarque bera test and its probabilities have been observed. Table-2 illustrates basic statistics for the daily closing prices of indices. The mean daily closing prices is maximum for FTSE/JSE SA All Share Index and minimum for KOSPI200. Skewness values indicate that FTSE/JSE SA ALSH, ASX200, GDAXI, KOSPI200, NEKEEI 225, NYSE, TSX Canada and CAC40 are positively skewed while closing prices of FTSE UK and MXX are negatively skewed. Kurtosis values indicate that KOSPI200 is leptokurtic while all other stock market indices are Platykurtic. The Jarque Bera test indicates that the p values of all indices are less than 0.05 which indicates that none of the indices closing prices are normally distributed.

Testing for Stationarity (Augmented Dickey and Fuller Test (ADF Test):

On each of the ten index series under consideration, ADF Test was performed. The significance of the test statistic is assessed using MacKinnon's critical values and the Schwarz Information Criterion (SBC), which determines the optimal lag duration. Table-3 Shows the results of ADF test:

The results indicate that all the ten indices are non-stationary at level since p values are greater than 0.05 and are stationary at first difference as p values are less than 0.05 in all the cases. Thus all series are I (1). The unit root null

Table-2 : Descriptive Statistics

	ALSH	ASX200	CAC_40	FTSE_UK	GDAXI	KOSPI200	MEXICO	NEKKEI _225	NYSE	TSX_CAN ADA
MEAN	57028.93	6085.091	5297.648	6947.017	12075.11	296.0479	45684.58	21540.51	10297 .57	16287.75
MEDIAN	54718.8	5916.3	5167.92	7018.6	12165.19	280.69	45250.34	21252.72	10086 .36	15617.3
MAXIMUM	80791.36	7628.9	7577	8014.31	16310.79	440.4	56609.54	33706.08	14689 .62	22087.2
MINIMUM	37963.01	4546	3595.63	4993.89	7692.45	199.28	32964.22	12834.01	6894. 22	11228.5
STD. DEV.	8923.85	753.478	896.1433	529.5194	2038.959	52.19396	4476.931	4675.5	2061. 672	2453.679
SKEWNESS	0.770919	0.37838	0.600945	-0.494999	0.157768	1.108847	-0.0557	0.223857	0.439 349	0.643735
KURTOSIS	2.958301	1.922634	2.495829	2.66533	2.242953	3.483368	2.607028	2.040045	1.990 248	2.445487
JARQUE- BERA	257.8247	182.8019	181.1979	117.5372	70.99615	525.4846	17.46933	114.2998	187.9 055	205.4307
PROBABILI TY	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0002	0.0000	0.000 0	0.0000
OBSERVAT IONS	2601	2531	2560	2583	2533	2448	2513	2445	2517	2509

Source : Compiled by the Author.

hypothesis has been rejected in favour of the stationary alternative in each case at first difference.

Testing for Randomness/Serial Correlation (Runs Test) - Non Parametric Test

The study's descriptive statistics for the chosen index returns demonstrate that the return series exhibit significant jarque-berra statistics, clearly demonstrating that they do not follow a normal distribution. As a result, using a non-parametric run test has additional significance. Run test has been employed in addition to examine the randomness of the observation and to determine whether the series followed a trend.

A data sequence that runs in a certain direction is known as a run. The results of run test have been incorporated in Table-4 as follows :

Table-3 : ADF Test

Indices	Criteria	level form			At first difference			Decisi on	
		Test statistics	P value level	Critical value (5%)	Test statistics	P value	Critical value (5%)		
R(nyse)	With intercept	-1.280452	0.6408	-2.8625	-	15.6439	0.0000	-2.8625	I(1)
	With intercept and trend	-3.823057	0.0155	3.41161	-	15.6405	0.0000	3.41161	I(1)
	None	0.856225	0.8948	1.94095	-	15.6024	0.0000	1.94095	I(1)
R(s&p/ts x)	With intercept	-1.779814	0.3909	-2.8625	-	15.1646	0.0000	-2.8625	I(1)
	With intercept and trend	-3.38435	0.0537	3.41161	-	15.1619	0.0000	3.41161	I(1)
	None	0.684939	0.8636	1.94095	-	15.1345	0.0000	1.94095	I(1)
R(mxx)	With intercept	-2.138785	0.2295	2.86249	-	47.4273	0.0001	2.86249	I(1)
	With intercept and trend	-2.540828	0.3082	-3.4116	-	47.4191	0.0000	-3.4116	I(1)
	None	0.50646	0.8249	1.94095	-	47.4271	0.0001	1.94095	I(1)
R(dax)	With intercept	-1.718266	0.4219	2.86248	-	51.1503	0.0001	2.86249	I(1)
	With intercept and trend	-3.553827	0.0341	3.41159	-	51.1404	0.0000	3.41159	I(1)
	None	0.782619	0.8821	1.94095	-	51.1361	0.0001	1.94095	I(1)
R(cac 40)	With intercept	-1.411179	0.5783	2.86247	-	50.9345	0.0001	2.86247	I(1)
	With intercept and trend	-3.286176	0.0687	3.41157	-	50.9263	0.0000	3.41157	I(1)
	None	0.853709	0.8944	1.94095	-	50.9192	0.0001	1.94095	I(1)
R(kospi)	With intercept	-1.381361	0.5929	2.86253	-	49.4499	0.0001	2.86253	I(1)
	With intercept and trend	-2.009286	0.5954	3.41165	-	49.4399	0.0000	3.41166	I(1)
	None	0.343659	0.7843	1.94095	-	49.4525	0.0001	1.94095	I(1)

R(ftse 100)	With intercept	-3.088639	0.0275	2.86246	-51.082	0.0001	2.86246	I(1)
	With intercept and trend	-3.390106	0.0529	3.41155	51.0722	0.0000	3.41155	I(1)
	None	0.158864	0.7322	1.94095	-51.089	0.0001	1.94095	I(1)
R(asx200)	With intercept	-1.803014	0.3794	2.86248	55.0274	0.0001	2.86248	I(1)
	With intercept and trend	-3.531806	0.0362	3.41159	55.0166	0.0000	3.41159	I(1)
	None	0.702175	0.867	1.94095	-55.021	0.0001	1.94095	I(1)
R(n225)	With intercept	-0.84855	0.8045	2.86253	49.8066	0.0001	2.86254	I(1)
	With intercept and trend	-3.396927	0.052	3.41166	49.8015	0.0000	3.41168	I(1)
	None	1.361157	0.9569	1.94095	49.7688	0.0001	1.94096	I(1)
R(jsesaal sh)	With intercept	-1.41579	0.576	2.86245	50.3503	0.0001	2.86245	I(1)
	With intercept and trend	-3.210114	0.0826	3.41154	50.3423	0.0000	3.41154	I(1)
	None	0.993654	0.9159	1.94095	50.3322	0.0001	1.94095	I(1)

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Table-4 : Runs Test

	TSX CANAD A	NYSE	MXX MEXIC O	GDAX I	FTSE UK	CAC 40	ASX2 00	KOSPI 200	NEKKE I 225	ALSH
Test value ^a	16287.75	10297.57	45684.58	12075.11	6947.017	5297.65	6085.09	296.05	21540.51	57028.93
Cases < test value	1559	1368	1356	1219	1197	1419	1476	1435	1293	1617
Cases >= test value	950	1149	1157	1314	1386	1141	1055	1013	1152	984
Total cases	2509	2517	2513	2533	2583	2560	2531	2448	2445	2601
Number of runs	58	46	58	52	50	46	32	30	46	54
Z	-47.682	-48.372	-47.851	-48.309	-48.894	-48.806	-49.052	-48.280	-47.631	-48.801
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

A. Mean

Source : Compiled by the Author.

The table clearly shows that the number of runs are 58 for TSX Canada and MXX Mexico, 54 for ALSH, 52 for GDAXI, 50 for FTSE UK, 46 for NYSE and CAC 40, 32 for ASX 200 and 30 for KOSPI 200. Analysis shows that returns of all the ten indices are significant as p value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 and hence are not random at all.

Testing for Equal Variances (Variance Test Ratio)

Variance ratio test is one of the widely used test for the claim that a time series follows a random walk or a martingale difference sequence. Variance ratio test has been applied on all the index series and results of individual and joint tests are shown in the table-5 and 6 respectively.

Chow |Z| denning statistic is 1.748368, 0.68947, 2.116152, 0.7436 and 2.023245 for NYSE, S&P/TSX, MXX, GDAXI and ASX 200 respectively which is associated with period two while the statistic for CAC 40 is 0.330439 for period 8, 0.631872 for KOSPI for period 4 and 0.433417, 0.678156 and 0.775705 for FTSE 100, Nekkei 225 and JSE SA ALSH respectively for a period 16. $P > 5\%$ in all cases which implies series are a martingale and not random walk.

5. Conclusion :

The research study was undertaken to examine randomness and weak form of efficiency in the stock markets of G20 countries. Several tests were employed to check the validity of Random Walk hypothesis. Normality, randomness stationarity and equality of variances were checked on the basis of Jarque Bera test, ADF test, Runs test and Variance ratio tests. The tests are indicative of the fact that the series were not normally distributed and were integrated at the order one i.e.. were found to be stationary at first difference and not at level data. Further Runs test and Variance ratio tests indicate that the series are not random and do follow a trend

The current work contributes to the body of literature by using unit root testing on G20 countries data and by taking heteroscedasticity into account for testing form of efficiency or random walk. The results are more crucial due to the fact that it has taken into account a period of a decade which is substantial enough to cover all sorts of reforms and changes in the economies and it is covering to G20 countries where as other studies have included Asian countries or BRIC countries to name a few.

Table-5 : Variance Ratio Test (Individual)

Indices	Lags (q)	VR(q)	STD ERROR	Z Statistic	Probability value
R(NYSE)	2	0.90078	0.05675	-1.74837	0.0804
	4	0.921172	0.107123	-0.73587	0.4618
	8	0.88235	0.163846	-0.71805	0.4727
	16	0.864923	0.231664	-0.58307	0.5598
R(S&P/TSX)	2	0.953303	0.067729	-0.68947	0.4905
	4	1.014519	0.127281	0.114071	0.9092
	8	1.068362	0.199879	0.342018	0.7323
	16	1.117006	0.278761	0.419737	0.6747
R(MXX)	2	1.054924	0.025955	2.116152	0.0343
	4	1.035252	0.049009	0.719291	0.472
	8	0.978803	0.078232	-0.27095	0.7864
	16	0.957248	0.114328	-0.37394	0.7084
R(DAX)	2	0.981056	0.025476	-0.7436	0.4571
	4	0.998583	0.050625	-0.02798	0.9777
	8	1.015175	0.085798	0.17687	0.8596
	16	1.01149	0.129367	0.088819	0.9292
R(CAC 40)	2	0.992438	0.028653	-0.26391	0.7918
	4	1.010417	0.056112	0.185654	0.8527
	8	1.031193	0.094398	0.330439	0.7411
	16	1.014548	0.139949	0.103952	0.9172
R(KOSPI)	2	0.997844	0.035272	-0.06113	0.9513
	4	1.040112	0.063482	0.631872	0.5275
	8	1.027486	0.096013	0.286278	0.7747
	16	1.054416	0.136855	0.397615	0.6909

(Contd...)

R(FTSE 100)	2	0.99486	0.031615	-0.1626	0.8708
	4	0.984639	0.05921	-0.25944	0.7953
	8	0.967006	0.097169	-0.33955	0.7342
	16	0.937873	0.143342	-0.43342	0.6647
R(ASX200)	2	0.909902	0.044531	-2.02325	0.043
	4	0.9267	0.085895	-0.85338	0.3935
	8	0.949915	0.134304	-0.37292	0.7092
	16	1.028439	0.191073	0.148839	0.8817
R(N225)	2	0.987699	0.029377	-0.41873	0.6754
	4	1.011882	0.052468	0.226455	0.8208
	8	0.986544	0.07888	-0.17059	0.8645
	16	0.922803	0.113833	-0.67816	0.4977
R(JSE SA ALSH)	2	1.012613	0.025672	0.4913	0.6232
	4	0.998242	0.053311	-0.03297	0.9737
	8	0.950347	0.087432	-0.56791	0.5701
	16	0.899333	0.129775	-0.77571	0.4379

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Table-6 : Variance Ratio Test (Joint)

Joint Tests				
Indices	Max z	Value	Df	Probability
R(NYSE)	Max z (at period 2)*	1.748368	2515	0.2849
R(S&P/TSX)	Max z (at period 2)*	0.68947	2508	0.9326
R(MXX)	Max z (at period 2)*	2.116152	2511	0.1304
R(DAX)	Max z (at period 2)*	0.7436	2527	0.9131
R(CAC 40)	Max z (at period 8)*	0.330439	2557	0.9955
R(KOSPI)	Max z (at period 4)*	0.631872	2437	0.9501
R(FTSE 100)	Max z (at period 16)*	0.433417	2582	0.9874
R(ASX200)	Max z (at period 2)*	2.023245	2530	0.1614
R(N225)	Max z (at period 16)*	0.678156	2426	0.9363
R(JSE SA ALSH)	Max z (at period 16)*	0.775705	2600	0.9002

Source : Compiled by the Author.

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